

METHODOLOGY FOR FUTURE TEACHERS OF BIOLOGY TO PERFORM INDEPENDENT WORK ON BIOTECHNOLOGY

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Annotation. This article presents suggestions and recommendations for future biology teachers to complete independent work assignments in biotechnology.

Keywords: biotechnology, independent work, creativity, professional competence, practical application, didactic tool.

One of the shortcomings of the educational process in higher educational institutions is insufficient attention to the implementation of independent work of students [1].

Today, it is advisable to use practical tasks in the development of creative thinking and professional competence of students studying in higher educational institutions [2].

Practical assignments are effective in developing the competence of future biology teachers in professional disciplines, including biotechnology. Examples of practical tasks in the field of biotechnology include the use of various tasks in field experiments and science laboratories using computer applications.

Failure to use the above tasks when performing independent tasks in the field of biotechnology leads to insufficient development of independent mental activity of future biology teachers. Therefore, the use of computer applications, field practices and research laboratories in organizing self-study of future biology teachers in the field of biotechnology is effective, so we recommend using the following structure to complete these practical tasks (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1. The structure of future biology teachers' practical assignments in biotechnology.

Computer applications are the main technical tool in independent learning. When planning independent work in the field of biotechnology, it is necessary to

give future biology teachers more practical tasks to be performed with the help of computers and to monitor their implementation.

It is advisable to prepare various presentations, tests, animation effects on the topic. As a result, independent work in the field of biotechnology is based on the use of computer technology to replicate the knowledge of future biology teachers and acquire new knowledge, as well as to improve their skills in working with computer applications.

At the same time, independent work in the field of biotechnology in field experiments and scientific laboratories will strengthen the theoretical knowledge of future biology teachers and will allow them to conduct experiments independently.

In conclusion, we recommend the use of the above-mentioned structure in the performance of independent work assignments of practical nature in the field of biotechnology by future biology teachers. Independent education based on this structure can lead to the development of creative thinking and professional competence of future biology teachers.

List of used literature

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